

PREPARATION OF 5 : 5-DIPHENYLHYDANTOIN

By J. SIKDAR AND T. N. GHOSH

An attempt has been made to explain the mechanism of the reaction in which benzil has been allowed to react with urea in presence of alkali to give rise to 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin.

5 : 5-Diphenylhydantoin, first prepared by Biltz (*Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 1379) and later rejected as having relatively small hypnotic effect, has now found use in the form of its sodium salt as an anticonvulsant in the treatment of epilepsy (Putnam and Merritt, *Science*, 1937, **88**, 525).

Hydantoin derivatives containing one or two substituents in position 5 are generally prepared from the cyanohydrin of an aldehyde or ketone containing the grouping $-\text{CO}, \text{CH}_3-$ by the action of urea (Pinner, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2351; 1888, **21**, 2320; 1889, **22**, 685) or ammonium carbonate (Bucherer and Steiner, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1934, **ii**, 140, 291). So far as the preparation of 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin is concerned, the method due to Biltz (*loc. cit.*) has now been found to be more suitable than those described above. However, this method, which consists in treating benzil with alcoholic alkali and then heating the mixture with urea, has not been hitherto studied thoroughly with regard to the mechanism of the reaction involved. As is well known, benzil, when treated with alkali, undergoes molecular rearrangement to benzilic acid. It was therefore thought that in the method of Biltz, benzil was first converted into the alkali salt of benzilic acid, which then reacted with urea to yield the alkali salt of 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin. But, curiously it has now been found that by heating under identical conditions the alkali salt of benzilic acid with urea in presence of alcohol, no reaction takes place.

With regard to benzilic acid rearrangement, Scheuing (*Ber.*, 1923, **56B**, 253) has shown that the potassium hydroxide addition compound of benzil forms within 2 to 3 minutes, whereas the rearrangement itself is a slow process. Ingold (*Ann. Repts. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **25**, 124; 1933, **30**, 177) proposed the existence of an intermediate negative ion (I), produced by the addition of hydroxyl ion to benzil, and indicated the importance of an alkaline medium in the transformation. Subsequent investigation by Roberts and Urey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 880) also indicates rapid, reversible addition of hydroxyl ion to benzil to form a negative ion (I), followed by a rearrangement.

In order to explain the formation of 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin by treating benzil with alcoholic alkali and then heating the mixture with urea, and the non-reactivity of the alkali salt of benzilic acid towards urea in presence of alcohol (*vide experimental*),

it is now surmised that urea reacts with the intermediate negative ion (I) and the complex, thus formed, next isomerises to the form (II), ultimately forming 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin by cyclisation :

The above mechanism of the reaction is supported by the following observations now made: (a) An alcoholic solution of benzil and urea, when heated, yields only diphenylacetylene-diureine (Angeli, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 606; Anschütz and Geldermann, *Annalen*, 1891, 261, 129). (b) If a solution of benzil in alcoholic alkali is allowed to stand at room temperature (28-30°) for about 10 minutes (time sufficient for the formation of the intermediate negative ion) before urea is added and the resulting solution heated, 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin and a trace of diphenylacetylene-diureine are formed. If the time allowed be even 10 hours instead of 10 minutes, the same reaction products are obtained and no benzilic acid has been isolated. (c) If a solution of benzil in alcoholic alkali is heated for only 15 minutes, cooled and treated with urea, and the resulting solution further heated, only benzilic acid is obtained and there is no formation of 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin, furnishing thereby further evidence in support of the mechanism that urea reacts with the intermediate ion (I) and the complex, thus formed, next isomerises to form (II). These observations further show that alkali is essential for the transformation of benzil to benzilic acid and that, although the formation of the negative ion (I) is rapid (*cf.* Scheuing, *loc. cit.*), it does not undergo rearrangement at ordinary temperature (28-30°), though the rearrangement can be effected very rapidly at higher temperatures.

An attempt was made to isolate the compound (before it underwent rearrangement) formed by condensing urea with the intermediate negative ion (I). With this object in view, the reaction of benzil with urea in alcoholic alkali has been studied at ordinary temperature but isolation of unreacted benzil and a trace of diphenylacetylene-diureine shows that heat is necessary for this condensation and once the condensation takes place, the condensed product readily undergoes rearrangement and cyclisation under the influence of heat.

However, it has also been found now that under drastic condition, viz., by heating benzilic acid with urea at 135°-140°, 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin is formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of Benzil with Urea.—An alcoholic solution of benzil (7 g.) and urea (4 g.) was heated under reflux for 1½ hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted

with a large volume of water. The solid obtained was filtered and extracted with hot alcohol. The alcoholic filtrate, on cooling, deposited a yellowish crystalline solid (2.5 g.) which was identified as unreacted benzil. The residue, insoluble in alcohol, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless, rectangular plates, m. p. 360° (decomp.), yield 2.8 g. Its identity with diphenylacetylene-diureine (Angeli, *loc. cit.*) was confirmed by mixed m.p. and a comparative study of the properties.

Reaction of Benzil with Urea in presence of alkali.—(i). The method of Biltz (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of 5:5-diphenylhydantoin was tried under different conditions and in every case, besides 5:5-diphenylhydantoin, a small quantity of diphenylacetylene-diureine was formed. Biltz, however, did not mention anything about the formation of the latter compound in this particular reaction.

The best conditions under which 5:5-diphenylhydantoin is obtained in maximum yield with the least formation of diphenylacetylene-diureine and the method of separation of the latter compound from the former are given below.

Finely powdered benzil (15 g.) was added at room temperature to a cold solution of sodium hydroxide (7.5 g.) in water (38 c.c.) and alcohol (30 c.c.). After 10 minutes powdered urea (7.5 g.) was added with stirring and the mixture was then refluxed on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted with a large volume of water, when a small quantity of a substance was found to remain insoluble. It was filtered, washed with water and was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless, rectangular plates, m.p. 360° (decomp.), yield 0.7 g. Its identity with diphenylacetylene-diureine was confirmed.

The above filtrate (after separation of diphenylacetylene-diureine) was cooled in ice and then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid, when a solid was obtained which was filtered and washed with water, next with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and finally with water. It was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless, rectangular plates, m.p. $294-96^{\circ}$ (decomp.), yield 11.5 g. (Found: N, 11.28. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.11 per cent). The above washing with aqueous sodium bicarbonate, on acidification under cooling, did not yield any solid, indicating thereby the absence of benzoic acid.

(ii). The above experiment was repeated only with the difference that the mixture of benzil, caustic soda and dilute alcohol was allowed to stay at room temperature ($28-30^{\circ}$) for 10 hours instead of 10 minutes, before urea was added and the mixture heated under reflux on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. In this case diphenylacetylene-diureine (3.5 g.) and 5:5-diphenylhydantoin (5 g.) were obtained and no benzoic acid could be isolated from the reaction mixture.

(iii). Powdered benzil (7.5 g.) was added at room temperature to a cold solution of sodium hydroxide (3.8 g.) in water (20 c.c.) and alcohol (15 c.c.), and the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 15 minutes, when a dark solution was obtained. The solution was cooled and urea (3.8 g.) was added. The mixture was again heated on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, cooled and then diluted with a large volume of water. The clear solution, on acidification under cooling with hydrochloric acid, yielded a solid which, after being thoroughly washed with water, was found to be completely soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate with effervescence. It was crystallised from boiling water (charcoal) in colourless, rectangular plates (6 g.), m.p. 150° . Its identity with benzoic

acid was confirmed by mixed m.p. with a genuine sample. Neither 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin nor diphenylacetylene-diureine was obtained.

Attempts to condense Benzilic Acid with Urea.—(i). Benzilic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in cold sodium hydroxide (2.5 g. in 12 c.c. water) solution to which alcohol (9 c.c.) and urea (2.5 g.) were then added. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The solution was cooled, diluted with water and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitate, thus obtained, was found to be completely soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate and after crystallisation from water it was proved to be unreacted benzilic acid, which showed that no reaction took place. Even when the conditions were varied, with the same reactants and solvents, no reaction took place.

(ii). An intimate mixture of benzilic acid (5 g.) and dry urea (2.5 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 135° - 140° for 6 hours. Ammonia and water vapour were found to evolve and the liquid melt gradually thickened. On cooling, a sticky mass, insoluble in water, was obtained, which was dissolved in cold dilute alkali and precipitated by hydrochloric acid. The solid was filtered, washed with water, next with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and finally with water, and was then crystallised from alcohol in colourless, rectangular plates (2.2 g.), m.p. $294-96^{\circ}$ (decomp.). Its identity with 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin was confirmed by mixed m.p. with the sample previously obtained and also by analysis.